

Territorial intelligence : The contribution Web 3.0 technologies in practice the territorial intelligence

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Abstract :

The term "Territorial intelligence 3.0" refers to the usage of the web 3.0 technologies, such as the mobile web, web applications and the semantic web, in the process of Territorial intelligence.

The territorial intelligence represents an offensive and a defensive attitude with all implications in terms of the information generated on global markets. The concept, the origin and the foundation of the above-mentioned term emerging in two distinct communities, one brings together practitioners of territorial intelligence developed around the institutional field, it is the case of top-down territorial intelligence. And the other community, brings together theorists searches in the multidisciplinary academic field, it comes from research on the economy, geopolitics, knowledge management and the discipline of information and communication technology sciences, this is the case of bottom-up territorial intelligence.

The Web 3.0 technologies, combine, on the one hand, web 2.0 technologies; the community Web (social networks: Linked in, Twitter, Facebook, etc.) and the collaborative Web (Wikipedia and Weblogs) (Quoniam & Lucien, 2009), and, on the other hand, smartphones, the internet of objects (Internet of Things), cloud computing technology and big data. "Web 3.0 is the combination of smart phones, social networks, Web 2.0, cloud computing and emerging business models as explained above" (Russell et al., 2016), web 3.0 practitioners consider that much of the world's information being correlated and frankly opening up to the general population, combine between these two concepts:

Generating the management strategic territorial information founded on Web 3.0 and working in favor of the territory.

There are generally two types of territorial intelligence 3.0. The first one is the top-Down Territorial Intelligence 3.0, it's the evolution of the national policy of competitive Intelligence 3.0 at the local level, but the term "competitive Intelligence 3.0" has been subjected to the same web evolution. And the second one is the bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0, it is manifested by the contribution of the actors of the territory in the process of local development through the technology of web 3.0.

The goal of our research is to propose a conceptual model base on a theoretical in the context of territorial intelligence in a digital sphere by web 3.0 technology. This model studied the process the contribute Web 3.0 technology to the practice of territorial intelligence and to meet them in.

Keywords: Territorial Intelligence , Web 3.0, Territory 3.0, Influence 3.0

JEL Classification : H75 L78, L86, M15, O14

Paper type: Theoretical Research

1. Introduction

The year 2007 brought a disruptive technologic transition, moving from the reign of Personal Computers toward the smartphones, which are connecting to cellular networks 3G or Wi-Fi, as well as accessibility support. And a user interface built around a multi-touch screen including larger screen sizes and the ability to install third-party mobile apps and offering a virtual keyboard. Their huge success confirms Bill Gates popularized idea, “Knowledge has become since then accessible via smartphone using fingerprint”.

the current 21th century is acknowledged by far as the information era (Cointot & Eychenne, 2014), the big-data creation never was this exponentially developing as it is now, but it will only become knowledge, if its significant in comparison to a referential, and able to ensure and enhance the company's sustainability, competitiveness and its performance (EL FADILI & GMIRA, 2015). Also, the knowledge can be a very effective weapon, when it is precise and threatening the actors's interests in their territories, changing the competitive balance and destabilizing the competition between territories. This strategic information immediately available at Fingertips is now providing guidelines for territory actors, institutional representatives and academic researchers in their decision-making process all by means of smartphones and tablets.

The territorial intelligence 3.0 reflects the use of the Web 3.0 tools to include the practice of territorial intelligence, as mobile web, web application and Semantic Web. In other words, the territorial strategic management of information founded on Web 3.0 working in favour of the territory.

From the standpoint of progressive development, competitiveness and attractiveness territory, national or local level, territorial intelligence represents an offensive and defensive attitude with all implications in terms of the information generated on global markets. There are two distinct approaches for territorial intelligence .

- Territorial intelligence top down is like implementation of process from behind competitive intelligence in the territory, it is the direct declination at the local level, the national policy of competitive intelligence (Pelissier & Pybourdin, 2009).
- Territorial intelligence bottom up, in this approach, the territories will be as endogenous actors for development locally, Additionally use networks of privileged suppliers and computerized research tools to help access the relationship resources and solutions (Pelissier & Pybourdin, 2009). Yann Bertacchini et al (2006) territorial intelligence is defined as information processes anthropological set up by territory actors, physically present or through ICT, which would appropriate the genetical resources locals and to create new solution for the development of endogenous projects (Bertacchini et al., 2006).

This paper aims to analyse how Web 3.0 technology can contribute to the practice of territorial intelligence and to meet them in the first part, it also allows the territorial Intelligence to review the definitions. And in the second part, after presenting the evolution of the Web, describes, how Web 3.0 technology can contribute to the practice of territorial intelligence.

2. Territorial Intelligence

The territory of an area of land is a precisely defined space subject to the the jurisdiction of a ruler or a state (Chambon, 2015). The Carayon report define the territory as the melting pot of economic activities juxtaposing traditional knowledge and advanced technologies. The promotion of their interests appears directly linked to their ability to organize themselves into networks, by adopting an approach based on the articulation and implementation of an

economic intelligence policy through competitiveness-attractiveness, influence, safety and training (Carayon, 2003).

The territory integrates companies and their economic dimensions, which constitute the sources of competitive advantages of the territory, which encompass all the actors, their resources as well as their capacity to create and mobilize specific non-transferable resources (Pelissier, 2009). It also includes the skills built and valued locally, constituting “*the key skills of the territories*” (Mendez & Mercier, 2006), which make it possible to attract foreign firms and investors to set up within this territory. On the one hand, that local is not neutral and the corollary of this approach for the globalization was being the ramp-up of the local territory for world's largest law firm, the territories are irreplaceable, since the nature of skills generate by the local, functioning of local markets and the nature of collective learning which enable, the information transmitted and exchanged by their members, which therefore make the companies choice (Longhi, 1997). In the other hand, the territory will be a central actor of the local competitiveness-attractiveness by self-development, funded by territorial learning. In this perspective, the new concept of territory merge as an actors for development, that is the factor of dynamism territorial based on competitive advantages created by territory, or recreated in order to their self-development (Menville, 1999).

This may be one of the reasons why territory intelligence adopted the management strategic territorial information. The territorial intelligence as well as the information process and exchanged by their members, the creating innovative territorial content likely to promote a collaboration and participation in new projects (Mericskay & Roche, 2011).

Territorial intelligence appears, one hand, as favorable offensive attitude for which the territory adopting a proactive strategy to meet an environmental mutation. And the other hand, as defensive attitude likely to reduce the impact of the unfavorable globalization factory and the economic warfare.

In an epistemological perspective of the concept of territorial intelligence, the origin and foundation of this concept emerging in two distinct communities, one brings together practitioners of territorial intelligence and developed around the institutional field, this is the case of top-down territorial intelligence. And the other community, brings together theorists searches in the multidisciplinary academic field, it comes from research on the economy, geopolitics, knowledge management and the discipline of information and communication technology sciences, this is the case of bottom up territorial intelligence.

2.1. Top-down territorial intelligence

The vision of competitiveness-attractiveness territory, top-down territorial intelligence show up as declining a local development, the national policy of intelligence competitive (Pelissier & Pybourdin, 2009). The territory is seen as an entity mesoeconomic which undergoes the attacks as a result of economic warfare, and particularly with regard to the informational warfare which can destabilize the data information between the environment territory (universities opinion, elected representative, research).

In this context, required for the implementation of a local development, the national policy of intelligence competitive (Pelissier, 2009). So as to raise public awareness and actor territory, face of new challenges and meet an environmental mutations. At first sight, the companies fall victim to destabilization operations by manipulation of information and cyber-attacks involving the use chat rooms, web sites, stock market expert and press commentary (Pelissier, 2009). On second thought to improve the business climate exchanges and partnerships of expertise available between public organization along with the private sector, in order to ensure reliability of the strategic information circulating within the territory. That is what we are calling the transferability capacities inside the territory.

Top-down territorial intelligence consist is to organize the synergy of public authorities at the local level and public-private cooperation in favor of government, which today passes through economic prosperity. This process participates in the public reform which aims to bring a strategist State and partnerships (Pautrat & Delebecque, 2009). In this perspective to the informational warfare, the role of the state is not limited to be interventionist in economic, but governments assumed a particularly important function as an enabling and developmental state to protect domestic industry. Also the state encourage companies to strive for excellence and reinforcing their competitive performance, even if this process can be inherently unpleasant and difficult (Porter, 1999). Thus acting on Carayon (2006) popularized the idea, “strategist state ” in competitive performance.

H.1.2.1.1 : Top down territory intelligence result the declination the national policy of intelligence competitive.

2.2. Bottom up territorial intelligence

With the aim of local development, the territory was contemplating an endogenous actor for development. For that matter, the territory is defined as a space which combining of the existing resource and bring added value, firstly this is the case of material resource ; geographic space, its natural resources, employment and equity, and secondly the immaterial resources like the identity of the local structure depending on its organizational memory and the same culture based on an historical continuation on the one hand, and on the other the resources built by territory as the alchemy between expertise available, tacit knowledge and organizational intelligence, in order to make their development policy succeed. It is like a space for valuing built resources according to a logic endogenous and an encourage knowledge-sharing according to a logic cooperative (Pelissier & Pybourdin, 2009), the territory provides by different interactions between the citizens, the CEOs of the companies, that politicians, non-governmental organizations and associations ... component this territories, that enable to mobilize and to create its specific resources non-transferable (Mendez & Mercier, 2006). This actors initiators makes this development like to an endogenous development founded by the territorial learning capacity. Xavier Greffe called these actors, “the civic entrepreneurs” which innovate while contributing to establish a new decision-making positions or an implementation of projects, they are civic (entrepreneurs) when they attempted to “optimize” the prospects for sustainable development and therefore beneficial to all in this territory (Pelissier, 2009).

Bottom up territorial intelligence emerges as regulation mode of information process, it is a participatory mode of governance (Pelissier & Pybourdin, 2009). Bottom up territorial intelligence is defined as information processes and anthropological, regular and continuous ,set up by locals actors physically present and/or remote which would appropriate the resources of the space by mobilizing then by transforming the energy of the territorial system through the project capability (Bertacchini et al., 2006).

H.1.1.1.1 : Bottom up territory intelligence result the initiative territory actors.

3. Territorial intelligence 3.0

3.1. From web 1.0 to web 3.0

Communication model for information from the Internet has undergone a remarkable evolution over the last three decades.

The first generation of Web 1.0: operated during the period 1989 to the end of 2005 (Hiremath & Kenchakkanavar, 2016) , described as the period of the "document web" and its information dissemination model, known as "one to many" is preserved by a competent

authority. That is to say, the producer of information, and Internet users not allowed to act on the information produced, "The idea behind the web 1.0 was to make a common information space within the internet user's and exchanging of communication through sharing information"(Hiremath & Kenchakkanavar, 2016).

Then the advent of Web 2.0 qualified as the web of Internet users, which upsets the distribution model and marks the transition from « one to many » to a communication model called « many to many ». That is to say, the transition from interactivity to interaction, thus contributing to the construction of networks that are no longer based on the exchange of information, but on the sharing of knowledge (Quoniam & Lucien, 2009). As pointed out by K. Gaberiel (2010) the users are no longer consumers, they produce content themselves: they are no longer readers of sites where publishing and updating require skills reserved for specialists, now they write their blogs, contribute to wikis, leave comments on the pages of visited sites, etc. (Gabriel, 2010).

Lastly, the emergence of the phenomenon of Web 3.0 qualified as the web of data or the semantic web. It is a new style of producing and receiving not just information, but above all knowledge and meaning (Andrade, 2013). Web 3.0 combines on the one hand web 2.0 technologies; the community Web (social networks: Linked in, Twitter, Facebook, etc.) and the collaborative Web (Wikipedia and Weblogs) (Quoniam & Lucien, 2009), and, on the other hand, smartphones, the internet of objects (Internet of Things), cloud computing technology and big data. Web 3.0 is the combination of smart phones, social networks, Web 2.0, cloud computing and emerging business models as explained above (Russell et al., 2016), web 3.0 practitioners consider that much of the world's information being correlated and frankly opening up to the general population. "The focus is on making data openly accessible, the Web of Data hosts a variety of data sets that include encyclopedic facts, drug and protein data, metadata on music, books and scholarly articles, social network representations, geospatial information, and many other types of information in some ways like a global database that most its features are included Semantics of content and links are explicit and the degree of structure between objects is high based on RDF (Resource Description Framework) model" (Karan, 2013).

Web 3.0 technology brings tools, applications and platforms and gives rise to new phenomena such as the Blockchain and fintech, which marks the appearance of a new mode of market finance qualified «finance 3.0» and thus disrupts traditional management towards new trends such as the liberated company, agile management in general qualified management 3.0 (Appelo, 2010); Aspects of social life are also concerned with Web 3.0: education, HRM, research, etc.

Education is qualified by education 3.0 (for example: the Coursera, Edx and Khan Academy app which gives the possibility to take online courses of different specialties through the intermediation of smartphones and tablets), Human resource management 3.0 (example of recruitment through LinkedIn which offers the possibility to capture and select different applications via the LinkedIn social network community.), and research 3.0 (the web 3.0 qualified as semantic web, and on the basis of this qualification the web 3.0 object, is to facilitate searches via semantics), Web 3.0 is the next generation of the Web and has already happened while moving to the smart phone era, whereby billions of users can be connected to the internet by their smart and portable devices that can connect them to different types of apps, services and communications (Russell et al., 2016).

H.2.1 : The Web 3.0 technology is inserting in human life.

The technology of Web 3.0 has been inserted in all areas, and in the disposition of all the territory actors, resulting from this insertion, the territory 3.0. but before that, territory 2.0, as "appropriation of web 2.0 by and for territory that has developed on the same model as the

concept of enterprise 2.0” (Depret, 2012). According to Depret, research on Territory 2.0 appears after the Kaplan and al. event in 2006 on City 2.0 as an open innovation platform, that is to say a city that gives everyone (public actors, large and small businesses, associations, individuals) the opportunity to imagine and innovate in clear, simple, transparent conditions that encourage partnerships (Kaplan & Marcou, 2009).

H.2.2 : The Web 3.0 technology is inserting in process the policy State.

3.2. Territorial intelligence 3.0

3.2.1. Definition

There are generally two types of territorial intelligence 3.0

Top-Down Territorial Intelligence 3.0: it's the evolution of the national policy of competitive Intelligence 3.0 at the local level, but the term "competitive Intelligence 3.0" has been subjected to the same web evolution.

- After the publication of Martre report in 1991, at that time competitive intelligence was fed by Web 1.0 tools, which results from this combination of competitive intelligence 1.0 which during the period from 1991 until the end of 2005. Meanwhile, the State extended its policy of competitive intelligence, the territorial intelligence 1.0 is therefore the result of this extension.
- Then, in 2006, the advent of Web 2.0, which changes the basic structure of information gathering with the 2.0 monitoring practices, that is to say, equipping social interactions within the monitoring process (Leitzelman, 2010), security and protection of information and the practices of influence through social networks, that is to say influence 2.0, as the case of the social network Twitter. As D. Ernotte Cunci, the managing director of Orange France, points out, "I tweet not as a person, but as a representative of my company, and therefore I forbid myself, for example, any relationship... any overly personal reaction that is not related to my business" (Claudine & Lorrays, 2013), these different practices converge towards competitive intelligence 2.0, such as the diffusion of the concept in the discipline is then materialized by an adaptation of informational practices, the informal structuring of a community of competitive intelligence. Finally, new methods of collecting and processing information (Quoniam & Lucien, 2009). And so, the emergence of territorial intelligence 2.0 during a period ranging from 2006 to the end of 2012.
- Finally, in 2013 the appearance of web 3.0 disrupts the mechanism of competitive intelligence practicable by a desktop or laptop computer, towards competitive intelligence 3.0 practicable by smartphones and tablets. Through Watch 3.0 embedded by the semantic web and aggregated by android applications, such as Diggo which allows sharing of websites, Images, Notes, Tags and annotations; Feedly which is based on RSS Feeds, and the protection of information and saving it on the cloud example of Google Drive and Dropbox, and finally the influence 3.0, for example «Power 2 influence» that allows to develop and improve the ability of influence of these users. Thanks to this appearance, territorial intelligence 3.0 is born

H.1.2 : Territorial intelligence 3.0 manifested by top down territorial intelligence 3.0

H.1.2.1 : Top down territorial intelligence 3.0 appeared win state use the web 3.0 technology to declinate the national policy of competitive intelligence.

Bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0 : it is manifested by the contribution of the actors of the territory in the process of local development through the technology of web 3.0, it is the case of the "Cities 2.0" programme, which encourages public actors, companies, researchers,

etc., to join forces to refocus the city's information systems around people, sustainable development and innovation." (Depret, 2012), in the same perspective web 3.0 users who are generally the actors of territory, as the case for the citizen who contributes to the development of his territory through the sharing of images and videos on social networks, and also contributes to the map of google maps and becomes as «Local Guide», the idea of citizen as sensors, whereby every human being is able to act as an intelligent sensor. Equipped with simple tools such as GPS, smart phones or instruments for measuring environmental variables, citizens are able to provide useful, effective and scientifically rigorous sources of observation" (Mericskay & Roche, 2011), and with the SmartCity project, as a territory residing in Internet of Things technology. In our view, we will consider the sharing and management of strategic territorial information by the territories themselves without the physical intervention of humans, it is the trend of connected objects that shares information, as in the case of a 'computer bot' application, i.e. a reboot application that interacts automatically with the client, as defined by A. Leonard (1998) is an autonomous computer program that is supposed to be intelligent, has personality, and usually, but not always, does a service (Leonard, 1998), an example of the Messenger bot (Facebook Corporate).

H.1.1 : Territorial intelligence 3.0 manifested by bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0

H.1.1.1 : Bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0 result the initiative the territory actors win use web 3.0 technology to join for development local.

The territorial intelligence 3.0 reflects the use of the Web 3.0 tools to include the practice of bottom up territorial intelligence and/or top down territorial intelligence.

H.2 : The territorial intelligence 3.0 reflects indirectly the using of Web 3.0 technology tools to include the practice of territorial intelligence

The literature review allows us to situate our subject in relation with territory intelligence 3.0.

Table 1 : Synthetic table of bibliographical references

Author-year-Journal	Country	Problematic	Method	Findings
Bertacchini, Y., de Conférences, M., Girardot, J.-J., & Grammacia, G. (2006) Revue d'archives en Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication	France	This paper studied the characteristics of what we call territorial intelligence as a theory, attitude, and ascending step of collective intelligence based on citizen approach of territorial valorization and, the capacity (or the incapacity) of the actors Co-to write the scenario	Theoretical research	<p>The territorial intelligence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • as information processes anthropological • set up by territory actors, physically present or through ICT, • which would appropriate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the genetical resources locals. ○ create new solution for the development of endogenous projects <p>the endogenous innovation territory to feeding at external information flow and at internal signals.</p> <p>Bottom up territorial</p>

		of their future within a widened framework, the U.E, in connection with local dimension		intelligence born win territory actors capitalizing the external information and internal signals for offers the local possible futures able to thwart the threat or uncertainty.
Claudine, B., & Lorrys, G. (2013) Communication et organisation	France	This article study the visibility, narrative identity and reputation of business leaders and their organization, through and/in digital social networks.	Dual method, A quantitative analysis of the data grossing up by the presence of French “big bosses” on these social networks, and a qualitative analysis for the CEO who speak in interviews offered by “Tweetbosses” about their presence on Twitter.	An place of the Twitter in the professional and family lives of chief executive officer (CEO). A willingness by the manager to use the digital social networks (web 3.0). The CEO invest in digital social networks to create and / or maintain social ties, or to create proximity with their audience, or to give themselves a modern image (influence 3.0).
Leitzelman, M. (2010), Lavoisier « Les Cahiers du numérique »	France	This paper analysis the effects of social and collaborative philosophy of the web change on intelligence practices that affect any knowledge worker	Theoretical research	The Web 2.0 changes the basic structure of information gathering with the monitoring 2.0 practices, that is to say, equipping social interactions within the monitoring process towards an ecosystem of interoperable and intelligent web 2.0 services.
Pelissier, M & Pybourdin, I. (2009). Lavoisier « Les Cahiers du numérique »	France	This article highlights the contradictions beteevn tow approaches of territorial intelligence co-exist with the vison of develeppement	Crossed visions of the territorial intelligence by mobilising tow discipline, the economics science and the information and	The top-down territorial intelligence is declination of national plicy a competitive intelligence at the local level. In endogenous logic the territory as a space for valuing buil resources. In cooperative logic the territory an encourage knowledge-sharing.

		<p>different.</p> <p>How top down territorial intelligence can syncornised with economie by insertied the human in sustainable development and the establishment the initiative territory actors ?</p>	<p>communication sciences.</p>	<p>The bottom up territorial intelligence like a mode of governance the information process.</p>
<p>Pelissier, M. (2009). Revue internationale d'intelligence économique</p>	<p>France</p>	<p>This article examined the conceptual identity of the territory.</p> <p>What is territory can be considered like central actor win use territorial intelligence, a same level of the company with competitive intelligence practice ?</p>	<p>A comparative study beteewen two divergent approaches of territorial intelligence co-exist, each based on a distinct conception of territory and development.</p>	<p>Two divergent approaches of territorial intelligence co-exist :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top-down territorial intelligence • Bottom up territorial intelligence <p>The top-down territorial intelligence can be considered lik the practic the competitive intelligence in local level for transfer the national competitive towards a territory local competitive.</p> <p>The territory as a space to valorisation of local resources built.</p> <p>The bottom up territorial intelligence as a strategic approach in the service of local development.</p>
<p>Quoniam, L., & Lucien, A. (2009) Lavoisier « Les Cahiers du numérique »</p>	<p>France</p>	<p>What phenomena imply an activity 2.0 when it brings into play an architecture of participation, a social architecture and an architecture of IT applications, shared, collaborative and distributed ? and</p>	<p>Theoretical research</p>	<p>The 2.0 phenomeno at a new paradigm of communication said “many to many” based on the sharing of knowledge by interaction beteewen different internaut.</p> <p>The competitive intelligence evolves and benefits of both a new mindest community network and new tools offered by Web 3.0 technology to become “competitive intelligence 2.0”.</p> <p>Three dimensions of web 2.0 :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The collaborative aspect,

		to what extent can we speak of competitive intelligence 2.0 ?		<p>based on user contributions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The semantic aspect, based on interoperability between the information itself thanks to tags or metadata which make it possible to mark information and organize technical interactions between applications. • The community dimension, involves building user networks. <p>The competitive intelligence is enriched by technologies for collecting and processing information 2.0 and ever more clustering engines are developing.</p>
<p>Russell, N., Victor, C., Robert, J. W., & Gary, B. W. (2016)</p> <p>International Journal of Information Management</p>	<p>The United Kingdom</p>	<p>This paper explored how the technology sector as a whole has facilitated modern businesses, and modern business model.</p>	<p>Theoretical research</p>	<p>Web 3.0 is the combination of smart phones, social networks, Web 2.0, cloud computing and emerging business models as explained above.</p> <p>Web 3.0 is the next generation of the Web</p> <p>Web 3.0 technology has already happened while moving to the smart phone era, whereby billions of users can be connected to the internet by their smart and portable devices that can connect them to different types of apps, services and communications.</p>

Source: Authors

3.2.2. Research model

To understand the territorial intelligence 3.0 process, we can refer to Figure 1.

The territorial intelligence 3.0 involves was practicing, the top down territorial intelligence 3.0 and/or bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0 (**H.1**).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the territorial intelligence 3.0

Source: Authors

The top down territorial intelligence 3.0 emerging by declination a national policy of competitive intelligence 3.0 in the local level, such as implementation the government policy of strategist state in competitive performance and reinforcing that process win authority use web 3.0 technology like social networks and develop the mobile web for transmits, diffuse the information will being correlated and frankly opening between different territory actors. In this perspective, web 3.0 technology inserting in process of monitoring, formulating, protecting and declinate the policy state a local level.

On the other hand, the bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0 result by initiative the territory actors, win these ones had been using web 3.0 technology to participle a development there local territory. These actors can be use the resource local to share information and to exchange expertise between others different actors in/out of their territory by using smartphone supporting at the web 3.0 technology to encouraging transfer, to valorization natural resource and to improving the competitiveness-attractiveness territory.

4. Conclusion

Territorial intelligence 3.0 refers to the use of the Web 3.0 technology, such as the mobile web, web applications and the semantic web, in the process of Territorial intelligence.

This paper study the contribution of the Web 3.0 technology in the practice of territorial intelligence and to meet them in, according to a two-step procedure. First, the exploratory systematic literature review by cross-referencing the ideas of different authors to situate our subject in relation with territorial intelligence 3.0 and to summarize their ideas in a table of bibliographical references. In a second step, to suggest a conceptual model based on a theoretical foundation in the context of territorial intelligence in a digital sphere by web 3.0 technology.

The Web 3.0 technology has been inserted in all areas, in the national policy, and on the disposition of all the actors of the territory. On the one hand, the initiatives of territorial actors whenever using the Web 3.0 technology how the sharing of information and the exchange of expertise by smartphone make the knowledge-sharing between territory actors as a endogenous local factor. That is the vision of bottom up territorial intelligence 3.0. In the other hand, the Web 3.0 technology is used by the authorities in process of monitoring, formulating, protecting and establish the state policy as a exogenous factor in a

local level, Collins, N & Bekenova, K, (2019) developed the concept of digital diplomacy how social media at Facebook “will radically change how diplomats engage with the populace in the countries to which they are stationed,”(Collins & Bekenova, 2019) towards to the new concept of success at your fingertips. Resulting from this perspective, the top down territorial intelligence 3.0.

Finally, the web 3.0 technology allow the promotion of harmonization between, the national policy declined as a exogenous factor, and the initiative of territorial actors to capitalize the external information and internal signals to offer the local a possible futures able to thwart the threat or uncertainty, as a endogenous factor, in order to seek the vision of competitiveness-attractiveness territory. This two factors cross in territorial intelligence 3.0.

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